

The Role of Time Reversal and Possible Number of Reactions on Equilibrium Part 2

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In Part 1, we argued that a reaction balance equation in statistical mechanics represents a statistical conserved quantity, i.e. the number of possible reactions of e_1 and e_2 which equals the number of possible reactions of e_3 and e_4 for $e_1+e_2=e_3+e_4$. In other words, as pointed out in Part 1, reaction balance as a conservation statement cannot stand alone, it must be linked with a second conservation equation, namely that of energy. In Part 1, we also tried to link these ideas to the existence of entropy.

Here we try to clarify some ideas related to entropy. In the Maxwell-Boltzmann, Fermi-Dirac and Bose-Einstein cases (to cite three examples), one has two basic conservation equations, namely $\sum_i p(e_i) = 1$ and $\sum_i e_i p(e_i) = E/N = e_{ave}$. One may ask the mathematical question: Does there exist a function $G(p(e_i))$ such that $\sum_i dG(p(e_i)) = A \sum_i e_i dp(e_i) + B \sum_i dp(e_i) = 0$ ((1)) ? In such a case, it seems that one would have to identify some portion of $G(p(e_i))$ with e_i , but that begs the question: How can one possibly do that a priori? We suggest that reaction balance (linked to a conserved statistical quantity, the number of possible reactions), allows for this because this statistical reaction balance cannot exist independently of energy conservation. Thus, one may see formally how terms in the reaction equation are linked to the e_i term in ((1)) and may construct $G(p(e_i))$ in that manner. As a result, $\sum_i G(p(e_i))$ is not an arbitrary math function, but is directly linked to the notion of a conserved statistical quantity due to the link between e_i and a function of $p(e_i)$ provided by reaction balance. We suggest that this might be a clearer way of considering the statistical nature of entropy than using various factorial expressions for the MB, FD and BE cases and then applying Stirling's approximation.

We also note that given $\sum_i dG(p(e_i)) = 0$ suggests that $\sum_i G(p(e_i))$ is itself a conserved quantity under $p(e_i) \rightarrow p(e_i) + dp(e_i)$ as we have argued in previous notes. As a result, the statistical nature of entropy seems to be directly linked to the statistical notion of a conserved number of possible interactions.

Conserved Number of Statistical Interactions

In the Maxwell-Boltzmann (MB) case, entropy is defined as $\ln(\text{number of states})$ through $\ln(N! / \prod_i n_i!)$. One may extremize these quantities subject to the a priori conserved quantity constraints: $\sum_i p(e_i) = 1$ and $\sum_i e_i p(e_i) = E/N = e_{ave}$. In the Fermi-Dirac (FD) and Bose-Einstein (BE) cases, more complicated arguments are needed to create an entropy factorial expression and we argue that one might feel that it does not have a completely clear definition.

We suggest that one consider reaction balance which seems to provide a very clear statistical picture for the MB, FD and BE cases. In these three examples, reaction balance states that the number of possible reactions of e_1 and e_2 must equal the total number of possible reactions of e_3 and e_4 if $e_1+e_2 = e_3+e_4$. In other words, one has two intertwined conservation equations, as pointed out in Part 1, and this is a key idea.

MB case; $NN p(e_1) p(e_2) = NN p(e_3) p(e_4)$ ((2a))

FD case: $NNNN p(e_1) (1-p(e_3)) p(e_2) (1-p(e_4)) = NNNN p(e_3) (1-p(e_1)) p(e_4) (1-p(e_3))$ ((2b))

The BE case is obtained using the FD result and changing the minus sign to plus ((2c))

One may then directly obtain the MB, FD and BE distributions by taking \ln of the above equations and associating them with $-e_1/T -e_2/T = -e_3/T -e_4/T$. ((3))

The point we make is that statistical features of the problem must be present in ((2a)), ((2b)), ((2c)). In other words, the statistical nature of the problem usually ascribed to entropy must already be sitting in ((2a)), ((2b)) and ((2c)). This feature is the equivalence of the number of possible reactions on each side of the reaction balance equation and we argue that the notion of entropy already has its roots here. One may argue, however, that reaction balance is clearly not an expression of entropy and so we consider how entropy formally arises in the MB, FD and BE cases.

Entropy

Given that $\sum_i p(e_i) = 1$ and $\sum_i e_i p(e_i) = E/N$ in the MB, FD and BE cases, one immediately has:

$\sum_i dp(e_i) = 0$ ((4a)) and $\sum_i e_i dp(e_i) = 0$ ((4b))

One may ask the mathematical question: Does there exist a function $G(p(e_i))$ such that:

$\sum_i dG(p(e_i)) = A \sum_i e_i dp(e_i) + B \sum_i dp(e_i) = 0$? ((5))

This question at first seems to have nothing to do with a statistical picture. The “catch”, however, is that for ((5)) to hold, $G(p(e_i))$ must contain an expression for e_i which is strictly expressed in terms of $p(e_i)$. In other words, we argue that $G(p(e_i))$ is strictly a function of $p(e_i)$ with no e_i values freely present. It seems that one cannot a priori know what $p(e_i)$ function should represent e_i unless one uses reaction balance which physically describes an interaction. Reaction balance represents a statistical conserved quantity and is also linked with e_i . Thus, the idea of a statistical function linked to e_i (i.e. $G(p(e_i))$) is present in reaction balance, we argue. This is an idea we suggested in Part 1, but would like to make more concrete here.

MB case: $\ln(p(e_i)) = -e_i/T$

$\sum_i dG(p(e_i)) = A \sum_i \ln(p(e_i)) dp(e_i) + B \sum_i dp(e_i) = 0$

One may see that $G(p(e_i)) = p(e_i) \ln(p(e_i))$ ((6a))

FD case, for which: $\ln(p(e_i)/(1-p(e_i))) = -e_i/T$. Then ((5)) becomes:

$$\sum_i dG/d(p(e_i)) dp(e_i) = A \sum_i \{\ln(p(e_i)) - \ln(1-p(e_i))\} dp(e_i) + B \sum_i dp(e_i) = 0 \quad ((6b))$$

$$\ln(p(e_i)) dp(e_i) - \ln(1-p(e_i)) dp(e_i) = d/dp(e_i) \{ p(e_i) \ln(p(e_i)) + (1-p(e_i)) \ln(1-p(e_i)) - dp(e_i) + dp(e_i) \} \quad ((7))$$

$$\text{One may write: } \sum_i G(p(e_i)) = \sum_i p(e_i) \ln(p(e_i)) + (1-p(e_i)) \ln(1-p(e_i)) \quad ((8))$$

$$-\sum_i G(p(e_i)) = \text{entropy} \quad ((9))$$

The Bose-Einstein result may be obtained by changing all minus signs in ((8) to plus signs.

The statistical nature of entropy seems to follow from the use of reaction balance to find an expression for e_i . This statistical nature of reaction balance is very clear, it is the number of possible reactions which may occur for e_1 and e_2 . Given that $\sum_i dG(p(e_i)) = 0$, $\sum_i G(p(e_i))$ has the form of a conserved quantity. As a result, one does not have to make use of factorial expressions which may have somewhat ambiguous interpretations. Furthermore, these interpretations are largely muted due to the drastic nature of Stirling's approximation: $\ln(n!) = n \ln(n)$, we argue.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we argue that reaction balance provides a clear picture of a conserved statistical quantity, i.e. the number of possible reactions of e_1 and e_2 . This conserved quantity, however, holds together with conservation of e_1+e_2 and so the two equations are intertwined. In other words, one has a function of strictly $p(e_i)$'s which is equal to $-e_i/T$ from reaction balance.

One may then ask: Is there a math function $\sum_i G(p(e_i))$ (strictly of $p(e_i)$ s) such that: $\sum_i dG(p(e_i)) = 0 = A \sum_i e_i dp(e_i) + B \sum_i dp(e_i)$? Given that e_i appears, it seems that one cannot possibly know of a $p(e_i)$ functional form for $p(e_i)$ unless one uses the reaction balance equation. Thus, $G(p(e_i))$, which starts as strictly a math function, becomes linked to a statistical picture of a conserved number of possible reactions. Thus, $\sum_i G(p(e_i))$ is statistical in nature, and not simply an arbitrary math function. Using reaction balance to replace e_i with a function of $p(e_i)$ allows one to readily solve for $G(p(e_i))$ for the Maxwell-Boltzmann, Fermi-Dirac and Bose-Einstein cases as we show above, with $-\sum_i G(p(e_i))$ being entropy.